

Achievable Rates of Phased Array-Fed Reflector Satellite Antenna Systems

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Abstract—This paper analyses the achievable rates of a geostationary (GEO) satellite system equipped with a phased array-fed reflector. Their aim is to achieve efficient spatial beamforming adaptability to traffic demands, which in the recent GEO satellite launches based on digitally transparent payloads is limited to programmable beams (i.e., beam-hopping) or applications with limited bandwidth. Low-Earth orbit (LEO) systems rely on direct radiating antenna (DRA) arrays to implement spatial reconfigurability, but due to the larger path loss, GEO satellites require a large number of antennas, which impacts the feeder link capacity and satellite mass and power. In this case, a relevant compromise solution is to consider the proposed phased array-fed reflectors that combine the adaptive beamforming capabilities of the feeding array with the reflector gain. We analyze this payload configuration considering its attainable rates, and analyzing the different configuration trade-offs related to the focal distance and the number of antennas in the feeding array. Numerical results show the design principles of this next-generation satellite payload.

Index Terms—phased array-fed reflector, defocusing distance beamforming, dirty paper coding, MMSE precoding.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the recent geostationary (GEO) satellite launches it has become predominant the use of digital transparent payloads [1], [2]. These space architectures are meant to dynamically optimize the offered capacity to the terminals in order to reduce the unmet capacity. These systems are limited by the beam pattern, which is generally produced by single-feed-per-beam (SFPB) array-fed reflectors. This beam pattern design is conceived considering the current operator's customers and their potential growth during the satellite's lifespan, which is generally 10-15 years.

The dynamic spectrum management of the mentioned systems provides the operator with an enabling technology to address unexpected traffic demands by relying on pre-emptive mechanisms and quick system spectrum upgrades. However, some variations of the spatial terminal distribution may require changes in the beam pattern in order to meet the client's traffic demand.

These satellite beamforming techniques were adopted in narrowband mobile systems [3]. As a general statement, beamforming matrices are multiplied at the ground station, and beamformed user signals are transmitted through the feeder

link. Consequently, the number of antennas and the user bandwidth are limited by the feeder link capacity.

Targeting wideband applications, current commercial non-geostationary (NGEO) satellite systems use direct radiating arrays to adapt the beam pattern to traffic demands. However, its application to GEO systems becomes a challenge. Indeed, while for NGEO the number of elements is reduced due to the required antenna array gain, for GEO systems thousands of elements are needed to overcome the path loss addressing the terminals demands [4]. This leads to increased payload mass, power and cost as well as to an unaffordable ground segment cost, (even considering next generation space-to-ground optical solutions) due to the required feeder link bandwidth.

A compromise solution is to consider a phased array-fed reflector (PAFR), which consists of a reflector illuminated by a phased array. The seminal work in [5] presented the opportunities of this architecture together with different solutions, including double-reflector deployments. It introduces the key role of the defocusing distance (i.e. the distance between the reflector focus and the feed-array position) and a conjugate field matching beamforming approach. However, it did not address how to select the defocusing distance nor the array size and their impact on the system capacity. The recently attracting attention on the PAFR concept is exemplified in [6] and [7]. Reference [6] focused on the antenna configuration (i.e. array size and defocusing distance) to achieve a given scanning range, but it did not evaluate nor optimize the resulting system capacity. The authors in [7] focus on the comparison of different beamforming solutions for a PAFR configuration, which balances multiple factors like array size, sidelobe levels or scanning range, but no optimization of this parameters is addressed. The system is analyzed in terms of carrier-to-interference power ratio for a traditional four-colour frequency reuse scheme.

In contrast to the mentioned works, this paper evaluates the PAFR solution from an information-theoretical point of view, considering the dirty paper coding capacity-achieving technique. Besides a practical benchmarking based on Minimum Mean Squared Error (MMSE) and full frequency reuse is also evaluated. The system is optimized in terms of number of antennas, users, and focal distances under the assumption of the same space platform cost. This is done by considering

the total power and bandwidth managed by the satellite to be the same for all configurations.

Considering that the electromagnetic modelling employed prevents us from providing closed-form results, we perform extensive numerical simulations. These results show that having more antenna elements reduces the user bandwidth and, in some cases, limits the overall system capacity.

The remainder of the paper is as follows. Section II presents the system model and the antenna modelling. Section III presents the beamforming techniques used in the evaluation. Section IV presents the numerical results. Section V concludes.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a forward link satellite channel where the payload is equipped with N antennas communicates with K single-antenna users. The received signal at the k -th user is given by:

$$y_k = \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{x} + n_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, K$$

where:

- $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the channel vector from the satellite to the k -th user,
- $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the transmitted signal vector from the satellite,
- $n_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{n_k}^2)$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at the k -th user,
- $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the Hermitian (conjugate transpose) operation.

The transmitted signal \mathbf{x} is a superposition of the users' data symbols with beamforming vectors:

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{w}_k s_k,$$

where $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the beamforming vector and s_k the unit energy transmitted symbol.

Clear sky conditions are considered in this initial analysis. For the sake of clarity, we can stack all channel vectors in a matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N}$. We now describe the modelling of \mathbf{h}

A. Antenna model

The satellite antenna under consideration consists of a PAFR constituted by a reflector illuminated by an array of horn elements. As a reflector, we assume an ideal planar reflectarray, as sketched in Fig. 1. It is composed of an array of square half-wavelength unit cells following a square grid, whose reflection coefficients are designed to synthesize a desired phase distribution on the reflector surface, controlling the far field radiation.

The radiation patterns of this antenna solution can be calculated by integrating the field at the reflector surface using the aperture field method, which process can be accelerated if the reflector is planar by the use of the inverse FFT [8], [9].

Specifically, we consider a center-fed circular reflectarray configuration. The reflector diameter is fixed to $D = 5m$,

Fig. 1. Reflectarray-based PAFR model

which is equivalent to 349425 half-wavelength square unit cells. The reflection phase synthesized by each unit cell is

$$\angle \Gamma(x, y) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + F^2} \quad (1)$$

where (x, y) are the coordinates of the unit cell with the origin at the center of the reflector and F is the focal distance.

In this way, the reflectarray produces a planar wavefront when illuminated from a spherical front originating at the focus, thus resembling the equivalent parabolic reflector depicted also in Fig. 1. The flat configuration of reflectarray antennas provide benefits in terms of cost, manufacturing process and deployment complexity with respect to parabolic reflectors at the expenses of reduced operational bandwidths, higher sidelobe levels and cross polarization.

In contrast to traditional SFPB antenna systems, the feed array is not located at the focal plane but at a certain defocusing distance dF from it. As a result, the beamwidth of the radiation pattern produced by each single feed is enlarged so that multiple feeds contribute to forming a narrow beam, providing the targeted beamforming flexibility. The optimization of the defocusing distance dF is part of the outcomes of this work.

The aperture field method is implemented as follows [8]. The radiated field from each x -polarized feed horn in spherical coordinates is modelled as

$$E_n^f(\theta, \phi, r) = \frac{jke^{-jkr} \cos^q(\theta)}{2\pi r} (\cos(\phi)\hat{\theta} + \sin(\phi)\hat{\phi}), \quad (2)$$

where subindex $n = 1, \dots, N$ refer to the feed antenna; θ , ϕ and r are the spherical coordinates; $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ are the unitary vectors in the polar and azimuthal dimensions; k is the wave number ($2\pi/\lambda$) and the exponent q controls the horn's beamwidth, which is directly related to the horn radius.

Using (2), we can calculate the incident field at each unit cell in the reflectarray surface. For each feed, the center of the spherical coordinate system is assumed to be in the

center of the feed aperture. The reflected field E_n^R in a cartesian coordinate system centered on the center of the reflectarray surface is obtained by multiplying the incident field, transformed to the cartesian coordinates centered at the reflectarray center, by the reflection coefficient Γ of each unit cell, thus

$$E_n^R(x, y) = \Gamma A E_n^f(\theta_l, \phi_l, r_l) \quad (3)$$

where $(\theta_l, \phi_l, r_l) \in \mathcal{R}$ where \mathcal{R} defines the unit cells positions defined in x and y ; and A is the transformation matrix from spherical coordinates centered at each feed to cartesian coordinates centered at the reflectarray center

The radiated field for feed horn n is then computed by integrating the reflected field on the reflectarray surface,

$$E_n^{rad} = \iint_{RA} E_n^R(x, y) dx dy, \quad (4)$$

which is done through the inverse FFT [8], [9]. Finally, the complex voltage gain of feed n is computed as [8]

$$G_n(\theta, \phi) = E_n^{rad}(\theta, \phi) \sqrt{\frac{4\pi r^2}{2\eta_0 P_f}} \quad (5)$$

where η_0 is the free space intrinsic impedance and P_f is the total power radiated by the feed:

$$P_f = \frac{\pi}{\eta_0 \lambda^2 (2q + 1)}. \quad (6)$$

The specific design of the reflectarray unit cells to achieve the reflection phase in (1), and the corresponding impact of reflection phase errors and magnitude variations, are out of the scope of this manuscript. An interested reader can refer to [8].

B. Channel Model

Given a user located at (θ, ϕ) , the channel vector can be computed via

$$[\mathbf{h}_k]_n = \frac{G_R G_n(\theta, \phi)}{4\pi \frac{d_k}{\lambda}} e^{j\Psi_k} \quad (7)$$

where G_R is the receiver gain, d_k is the distance between the satellite and the terminal, $\Psi_k = (2\pi/\lambda)d_k$ is the phase rotation due to the signal propagation.

III. OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

In this paper, we focus on the satellite system capacity under the assumption of a limited feeder link bandwidth. This value is assumed to be B_F so that the attainable sum-rate becomes

$$MSR = B_u MSSE, \quad (8)$$

where MSSE is the Maximum Sum-Spectral Efficiency and B_u is the user bandwidth which is limited by B_F/N . In this channel model, the MSSE can be obtained via the dirty paper coding capacity upper-bound $\mathcal{C}_{DPC}(\mathbf{H})$ as reported in [10] and P the total transmit power.

Note that in (8) we can only have access to the global attainable sum-rate whereas it is not possible to determine any

individual maximum rate. This is due to the considerations of the information-theoretical bound of the DPC approach. Moreover, the DPC formulation in [10] considers full-power constraints, so there are no restrictions about how P is distributed through all antennas.

It is well-known that the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H$ govern the attainable rates in (8). Unfortunately, our antenna modelling prevents us from providing closed-form insights regarding this distribution. Alternatively, we aim to optimize the antenna configuration in order to obtain the maximum in (8).

From an antenna design point of view, maximizing (8) has different implications. In fact, fixing the reflector diameter and F/D ratio, a target region of interest (ROI), an available feeder link bandwidth and a maximum power available per antenna yields to clear design tradeoffs for the feed-array configuration.

First, the array aperture needs to be large enough to cover the region of interest. Note that the beam scanning capabilities largely depend on the distance between the feeds at the array edges and the focal axis. Large array apertures can be synthesized by: (i) increasing the number of antennas, which implies a reduction of the available user bandwidth since the required feeder link bandwidth scales with the number of antennas; or (ii) by increasing the spacing between feed elements (and maybe the apertures of the feeds too), which implies the raising of grating lobes if the array is not placed at the focal plane ($dF = 0$ cm).

Indeed, due to the per-antenna power constraint, $dF > 0$ is favourable since it allows combining the power of multiple feeds to form a single beam, so grating lobes can be expected for large inter-element spacings. Using $dF > 0$ permits also reducing the array aperture due to the large beamwidth provided by each feed. However, such a reduction may have an impact on beamforming performance if fewer feeds cover the edge of the ROI.

Considering a fixed array size of L , we opt to consider different inter-spacing values in order to vary N . Bearing this in mind, we aim to optimize

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{N, dF}{\text{maximize}} && MSR \\ & \text{subject to} && 0 \leq N \leq N_{\max} \\ & && 0 \leq dF \leq dF_{\max} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where N_{\max} and dF_{\max} are the maximum number of antennas and focal distance. This problem is a mixed-integer non-linear problem which is known to be very hard to solve. As we do not even have access to a closed-form of the objective function, we opt to perform a grid search over different values in order to obtain efficient points.

For the sake of completeness, we also include the performance considering a practical closed-form solution such as the so-called Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) beamforming [11] with per-antenna power constraints. It can be written as

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{MMSE}_u} = \left(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H \frac{P}{NK} + I_K \right) \mathbf{H}^H. \quad (10)$$

We consider the power normalization coined in [4] as CTTC normalization which involves first normalizing each column of (10) to be unit norm

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{MMSE}_{n_c,k}} = \mathbf{w}_{\text{MMSE}_{u,k}} / \|\mathbf{w}_{\text{MMSE}_{u,k}\}\|, \quad (11)$$

and then we impose that each of the antenna elements operates at maximum transmit power P/N . This normalization scheme not only forces all amplifiers to work at their optimum working points providing efficiency benefits but also provides sum rate improvements when compared with traditional normalization keeping the relative amplitude ratios of (10) in practical moderate to low Signal-to- Noise Ratio (SNR) regimes [4]. With this beamforming technique, the sum-rate can be written as

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{B_F}{N} \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k), \quad (12)$$

where

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{w}_k|^2}{\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k}}^K |\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{w}_j|^2 + \sigma_{n_k}^2}. \quad (13)$$

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

As a result of the antenna modelling presented in the previous sections, we extensively perform a numerical analysis of the payload under investigation. We first show the beamforming solution when varying N and dF and, after, we present the attainable rates \mathcal{MSR} . Finally, we consider a system-level analysis of the most convenient architecture.

A. Feed-array configuration tradeoffs

Figs. 2 and 3 exemplify the antenna design trade-offs. They compare the beams at coverage center and edge for circularly-shaped feed-arrays with 27 cm of diameter composed by 127 feeds of 1.5λ diameter, 301 feeds of λ and 822 feeds of 0.6λ . The horn feed arrangement follows a hexagonal grid. The frequency of operation is fixed to 20 GHz. The defocusing distance is set to $dF = 0, 20.25\text{cm}$ in Fig. 2, 3, respectively.

A significant gain difference between the two figures can be observed due to the per-antenna constraint and the capability to combine power from different feeds when $dF > 0$. However, Fig. 3 shows the raising of grating lobes with the combination of $dF > 0$ and large elements (and inter-element spacing). It also shows better coverage at ROI edges as expected. Let us remark that, although the best performance is obtained with the largest number of elements, this implies a direct reduction of the user bandwidth, which needs to be compensated by the number of users served with good SINR conditions. A numerical analysis is performed later to evaluate this trade-off.

B. MSR performance evaluation

We now analyze the trade-offs on the feed-array configuration using DPC capacity bound and MMSE beamforming under per antenna power constraints and then we evaluate the beamforming techniques proposed in the previous section. The

Fig. 2. Comparison of synthesized beams at coverage center and edge for different array sizes placed at focal plane

Fig. 3. Comparison of synthesized beams at coverage center and edge for different array sizes with a defocusing distance $dF = 20.25\text{cm}$

scenario under test corresponds to the downlink of a transparent GEO satellite with regional coverage. Unless otherwise stated, the used simulation parameters are summarized in Table I.

In particular, we consider a ROI of 3.11° . The analysis starts by identifying the minimum feed-array aperture providing the coverage of 3.11° , which, as shown in Fig. 2-3, is found to be of 27 cm in diameter. Fixing this aperture size, we perform a sweep over different defocusing distances in the range $dF = 0 - 40.5\text{cm}$. The three feed horn aperture sizes identified in Section are evaluated (*i.e.* feed horn diameters of 1.5λ , λ and 0.6λ , providing arrays with 127, 301 and 822 elements and user bandwidths of 40 MHz, 16.9 MHz and 6.2 MHz, respectively).

We first show the attainable rates deriving from evaluating (9). As depicted in Fig. 4, we show \mathcal{MSR} for three different N which involve modifying the inter-element spacing as in the previous subsection and $K = 250$. It can be observed that the use of a smaller number of elements while keeping the antenna

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Definition	Value
lon_s	Satellite longitude	115.82°
(lat_c, lon_c)	Position of the center of ROI	(11.03°, 115.82°)
r_{ROI}	ROI radius	4000 km (3.11°)
f	Frequency	20 GHz
B_F	Feeder link bandwidth	5.08 GHz
B_u	Users' bandwidth	B_F/N
D	Reflector diameter	5 m
F	Focal length	2.4792 m
N	Number of array elements	127-822
D_e	Element diameter	$1.5\lambda - 0.6\lambda$
d_f	Defocusing distance	0, 40.5 cm
Array grid	Array grid	hexagonal
P_t	Available power	3175 W
P_e	Available power per element	P_t/N
N_u	Number of users	variable
G/T	Users' G/T	16.3 dB
Channel	Channel model	LoS
q	Cosine exponent factor	5.8, 2.6 and 1.3

Fig. 4. MSR vs focal distance for different inter-element spacing and $K = 250$.

size with 1.5λ results in a substantial gain of the attainable rate with all dF values. In light of the previous results on the resulting beampattern, the effect of grating lobes is limited in terms of system capacity.

The effect of dF does not seem to be very strong for all N values. In any case, there is an optimal value which is different for each N . This is mainly due to the gain versus grating lobes trade-off.

C. System analysis

We now consider the effect of the number of user terminals (K) and usage of MMSE precoding. Bearing in mind this, for each dF value, we perform a sweep on the number of served users K , and for each K value, a Monte Carlo simulation with 100 realizations is carried out. In each realization, the users are randomly located according to a uniform distribution. No specific scheduling is considered.

For this evaluation, we focus on the DPC capacity as an upper bound and the MMSE as a benchmark. Since the MMSE allows identifying an optimum number of users K_{opt}

Fig. 5. Maximum sum-rates obtained at K_{opt} with MMSE precoding as a function of dF for the different array configurations

that maximizes the sum-rate (as shown in Fig. 6), Fig. 5 evaluates how the sum-rates obtained at these working points vary with the defocusing distance for the different feed-array configurations.

A clear optimum dF value can be identified for each array configuration, which balances the available user bandwidth, the power combining through multiple feeds, the grating lobe levels, and the coverage at ROI edges. The best balance is achieved by the array using λ aperture horns. Remarkably, the solution with 0.6λ aperture horns provides poor results despite it generates the *best* beams in terms of gain and beamwidth, as shown in Fig. 3. The reason for that is that due to the very limited user bandwidth, large number of users need to be served to achieve comparable sum-rates, but the synthesized beams are not good enough to handle the resulting interference from the large user density.

Fig. 6 depicts the sum-rate variation with the number of users for the optimum defocusing distances identified. The optimum number of users are $K_{opt}=90, 220, 250$ for the arrays with feed horn diameters of $1.5\lambda, \lambda$ and 0.6λ .

At K_{opt} working points, the benchmark MMSE beamformer is able to provide 63.8%, 56.6%, and 55.3%, respectively, gap with respect to the upper-bound. Note, however, that the DPC capacity here does not consider the per-antenna power constraint. Let us remark also that beyond the optimum K_{opt} , the DPC capacity keeps increasing but there is no way to ensure that all users are served, so a kind of implicit user scheduling may be applied. Hence, it is expected that user scheduling can further close the gap between DPC and MMSE.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated PAFR satellite payload from the achievable rates point of view keeping the antenna size, power and bandwidth constraints. An antenna model was used to evaluate the novel architecture efficiently. The evaluation showed that in some cases, having more antennas does not necessarily yield an efficient configuration. Alternatively, the

Fig. 6. MMSE sum-rates and DPC capacity obtained at optimum dF values as a function of the number of users K for the different array configurations

defocusing distance plays a role in the system, and its optimal value depends on the number of users to be served.

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